

ENVIRONMENTAL POLICIES, ISSUES & EXECUTION

Savita Khare

Prof. Home science dept

ABSTRACT

While India has gone through a rapid period of economic growth in recent years, country's environment has paid a heavy price in form of deforestation, pollution & threats to endangered species. India's current environmental policy is dominated by the landmark National Environment Policy 2006. This paper discusses Indian Environmental Policies, major Issues & Execution of policies.

HISTORY

From ancient time Indian society focused on conservation of environment. Arthashastra mentioned in Vedas prescribed punishment for damaging forest. British period saw beginning of organized forest management focusing on wildlife & water pollution.

Forest Act of 1865 was enforced for the first time to establish state monopoly over forests. Bengal Regulation VI of 1819 first protected water resources. Restriction on fouling of water was imposed under Shore Nuisance (Bombay & Kolaba) Act of 1853 and the Oriental Gas Company Act of 1857.

FORMALIZATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLICIES

Environment policies in India were first drafted by British India under Indian Forest Act in 1927. It was mainly focused on regulation of forest produce especially timber.

Major revision in policies was done in 1972 under Wildlife Protection act focusing mainly on animal protection & banning trade of animal made products. National Board and State Boards for Wildlife were developed followed by formalization of national parks, wildlife reserves & sanctuaries.

Environmental policies were further amended under different five year plan. Major regulations were made in 1980 & further in 1988 under Forest Conservation act where Central government played a significant role in protecting environment. Under this act, no state government (or any authority) have right to: a) Cease forest reserve, b) Use forest for non-forest purpose, c) Forest land can be cleared of trees only for purpose of reforestation, d) forest land can only be leased to private person or non-government authority.

Legislative measures taken during in 80's: a) Forest (conservation) Act 1980 -Amended in 1988, b) Air (prevention and control of pollution) Act 1981 -amended in 1986, c) Biosphere reserve program, d) CITES (convention of international trade in endangered species), e) EPA Act 1986 f) Motor vehicles amendment Act 1988.

Major National environmental policies were amended in 2006 covering:

- Strategy-formulation for environmental protection,
- Analysis of land degradation,
- Adoption of land-use practices,
- Focus on Multi-stakeholder partnerships,
- Agro-forestry promotion,
- Organic farming adoption

Source: Wildlife Institute of India, 2009

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ISSUES IN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICIES IMPLEMENTATION

As per World Bank study, India has made fastest progress between 1995 & 2010 in addressing environmental issues and improving quality.

Pollution and proper sanitation is one of the major challenges in India. The air pollution in the big cities is rising to such an extent that it is now 2.3 times higher than the amount recommended by WHO.

Major environmental issues in India:

- Forest and Agricultural land degradation.
- Resource depletion- water, minerals, forest, sand, etc.
- Public health
- Loss of biodiversity
- Loss of resilience in eco-systems
- Poor water supply and sanitation issues

- Natural hazards like floods, annual rainfall due to deforestation.
- Poor agricultural practices
- Economic development & growing population is also considered as cause of environmental issues.

ENVIRONMENTAL POLICIES EXECUTION IN INDIA

With increasing environment awareness, government of India along with different state governments has started different programs to protect environment:

Gujarat: XGN – Xtended Green Node is a web enabled software that was first implemented in Gujarat in 2008 to monitor day to day operations at any State Pollution Control Boards in India. This system has been replicated and is now being used by other States including H.P., Uttaranchal, Goa, Andhra Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh.

A third party monitoring scheme has been launched by GPCB in 1996 to monitor industrial effluent quality.

Maharashtra: MPCB has initiated a Water Quality Monitoring Network in Maharashtra with Groundwater Survey and Development Agency (GSDA) & Central Ground Water Board. GSDA and CGWB is monitoring groundwater in 35 districts at around 1400 villages.

Tamil Nadu: TNPCB has initiated the CARE AIR programme (Centre for Assessing Real Time Air Quality) for monitoring all the industrial emissions in Tamil Nadu on real time basis and to analyse the trend of emissions into the atmosphere.

Madhya Pradesh: MP PCB has taken special initiatives for the collection and disposal of non-recyclable polythene waste from towns in MP. The non-recyclable polythene waste is collected through NGO's at pre-defined rates and transported to cement plants where the waste is used as a co-fuel in the cement kilns.

Punjab: The Punjab Pollution control board has been instrumental in facilitating the installation of Zero Liquid Discharge (ZLD) in 8 large/ medium scale industries.

Andhra Pradesh: State Board has promoted implementation of zero liquid discharge mainly for pharmaceutical industries 2009.

Sectors Contributing the Most to Air Pollution in the Six Cities

Major Causes of Wastage of Water in the Six Cities

Changes in the State of Tree/Forest Cover and Plant Species in the Past Five Years

Sectors Contributing the Most to Air Pollution

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